

PARENTING STYLE AND SUPPORT FOR LEARNERS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG PRIVATE SCHOOLS

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Parenting Style and Support for Learners' Academic Performance among Private Schools

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Abstract

This study sought to answer the level of parents and learners' respondents on their assessment of parenting styles and support; to determine the learner's academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English; and to analyze the significant relationship between the parenting style and support on learners' academic performance. The respondents of the study were 100 parents and 100 learners of Grades 5 and Grade 6 in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City for the School Year 2021-2022. A descriptive-correlational research method was used, and a patterned and modified questionnaire. Moreover, all the data gathered were tallied and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that parents manifested a high authoritative parenting style. Meanwhile, they exerted higher support in terms of parental support in education than financial support, and the learners' got outstanding academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English in the First and Second Quarters. Furthermore, the learners' academic performance was not statistically significant to parenting styles. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. While parental support and learners' academic performance in Science has no significant relationship, the null hypothesis was accepted. Meanwhile, Mathematics and English had a significant relationship to parental support. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. The researcher concluded that parental support greatly impacted learners' academic performance in Mathematics and English, unlike parenting styles, which did not influence the learners' academic performance.

Keywords: *parenting styles, support, academic performance*

Introduction

Parenting is a complex task for parents' child-rearing. It requires appropriate approaches and adequate engagement time to effectively develop a child's well-being. In such a way, parents explore, adopt, and manifest different parenting styles and support, for they want to give only the best for their children. Some parents were not as effective as possible because of the wrong manifestation of parenting and lack of parenting support. Parenting styles involve parents' actions, behaviors, beliefs, values, expectations, rules, and reactions demonstrated towards their children. While parenting support refers to a parent's active and ongoing involvement in their child's academic journey. Parents must need to know and have a better understanding that parenting styles and support are influential factors in learners' academic performance.

In line with these, the Department of Education places high regard on the education of every Filipino learner. Part of their mission and vision is to help every Filipino learner realize their full potential, to serve their stakeholders continuously, to protect and promote quality and equitable basic education, to provide a motivating environment for every learner, and to actively engage all stakeholders and share responsibility in developing life-long learners. Thus, the Department of Education implemented different DepEd orders to encourage parents' participation to help their child's academics. For instance, a DepEd Order No. 23, s. 2016, enclosure no.2, that school was advised to conduct a conference every quarter to appraise parents on their children's performance at school and to remind and ensure parental involvement in their child's school activities. Another, DepEd Order No. 54, s. 2009 on the Revised Guidelines Governing Parents- Teachers Association (PTA) at the school level, where parents are considered as group support and significant partners of the school in guiding and supporting their children's academic needs. In addition, DepEd Order No. 24, series of 2008, the implementation of "Brigada Eskwela". One of its goals is to encourage understanding among stakeholders, especially parents, that education is everyone's responsibility. At the same time, this program promotes volunteerism, Bayanihan Spirit, and camaraderie to build oneness and collaboration among parents and stakeholders. Certainly, when children observe and notice their parent's presence at school, it will boost their self-confidence and create a good impression of doing well at school.

The Department of Education was tasked to address the crisis of the poor performance of grade 4 students in the International Assessment of Mathematics and Science. According to Trends in International Mathematics (TIMSS) 2019 study, it was revealed that out of the 58 countries that participated in the examination, the Filipino grade 4 students were the lowest in rank. Wherein the Philippines scored 297 in Mathematics and 249 in Science. The results of the scores were "significantly lower" compared to other countries. In the same year, 2019, a separate study by the Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Association (SEAMEO) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), only a small percentage of Filipino Grade 5 students outdo themselves in Mathematics,

Reading, and Writing. Furthermore, in November 2020, a Switzerland-based education company also disclosed that the Philippines dropped in the global English proficiency ranking. To add, another study by Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) revealed that Filipinos were 2nd lowest among 79 countries, specifically in Reading, Mathematical and Scientific literacy.

With these, the researcher felt the need to investigate the underlying reasons that contributed to these poor performances among Filipino learners in connection to factors such as parenting styles and support provided to their children; learners' academic performance in

Mathematics, English, and Science; and the relationship between parenting styles and support on learners' academic performance. Thus, this study was conceived.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the parenting style and support for learners' academic performance among private schools in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City for the School Year 2021- 2022. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what level the parents' and learners' respondents assess the following:
 - 1.1. Parenting Style:
 - 1.1.1. authoritative; and
 - 1.1.2. permissive – indulgent?
 - 1.2. Support:
 - 1.2.1. financial; and
 - 1.2.2. education?
2. What is the level of learner's academic performance in the following areas:
 - 2.1. Mathematics;
 - 2.2. Science; and
 - 2.3. English?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the parenting style and support on learners' academic performance in Mathematics, Science and English?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational design. A Correlational Design is a descriptive and non-experimental design that measures a relationship between two or more variables without controlling either of them. It aims to investigate whether there is a positive, negative, or zero correlation between two or more variables (McCombes, 2019).

This study described the parents' and learners' respondents assessed the parenting styles: authoritative and permissive-indulgent and support in terms of financial and education. In addition, the level of learners' academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English in the First and Second Quarters was being determined. The descriptive-correlational design was used by the researcher in this study to describe the parenting styles and support exerted by the parent respondents to their children and the level of academic performance shown by their children. The researcher examined the relationship between the two variables that enabled them to make predictions about the variables.

Participants

The respondents of the study were the 100 parents and 100 learners of Private Elementary Schools in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City for the School Year 2021-2022. A purposive sampling technique was utilized to determine the number of parents and learners' respondents. The researcher opted to determine 10 parents' and 10 pupils' respondents per school to have an equal representation of the sample. Table 1 below shows the sample size per school.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

Schools	Respondents			Total
	Parents	Learners		
		Grade 5	Grade 6	
PHINMA Cagayan de Oro College- Grade School Department	10	5	5	20
Liceo de Cagayan University-Grade School Department	10	5	5	20
Diamond Evangelical School	10	5	5	20
Christian School for Life	10	5	5	0
Summer Hill School Foundation Inc.	10	5	5	20
Merry Child School	10	5	5	20
Opol Grace Christian School	10	5	5	20
HappyLand International School	10	5	5	20
Cagayan de Oro Christian School	10	5	5	20
King of Zion School	10	5	5	20
Total	100	50	50	200

Instruments

The study utilized a patterned and modified questionnaire from Munyi's (2015) thesis entitled, "Influence of Parenting Styles on Academic Performance of Adolescents in Secondary Schools: A Case of Manyatta Constituency," Moneva et al. (2020) in their study about "Parental Financial Support and Students Motivation in Learning," and Kimaro and Machumu (2015) in their research about "Impact of parental involvement in school activities on academic achievement of primary school children." In addition, the researcher made some modifications to some terminologies or word usage, construction, and composition of sentences.

The researcher instruments for parents have two parts. Part I deals with the level of parents' assessment of parenting styles. Part II deals with the level of parents' assessment of parental support. While the learners have three parents, Part I and Part II are the same as the parents, and the addition of Part III deals with the level of learners' academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English. Each variable was assessed considering the following: authoritative parenting styles (10 items) and permissive-indulgent (10 items). While support in terms of financial (10 items) and education (10 items), and the learner's academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English in the First and Second Quarter of the School Year 2021-2022.

Reliability Test and Validity of Instruments

The items of the instruments were subjected to a test of validity and reliability. To establish the instrument's validity, the researcher requested the panel members to evaluate its content. Therefore, the researcher conducted a pilot testing at Camp Evangelista Elementary School, Cagayan de Oro City, last January 10, 2022. The result of the computation using the Cronbach's Alphas coefficient of reliability was, for the parents' questionnaire, the result was .876, which means "good" of its internal consistency. While learners' questionnaire was .923, which means "excellent," considering that .70 was the passing rate result.

Procedure

Before the administration of the survey questionnaire, the researcher observed some protocols due to the pandemic. This was to ensure the safety of the persons who may accommodate the researcher during the process of acquiring approval to conduct the study. The researcher approached the Dean of Graduate Studies and asked for a letter of request to conduct a study on ten (10) elementary private school respondents in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City. After the letter was given, the researcher proceeded to the ten (10) private elementary schools and asked permission from the principal to conduct the study.

Due to COVID-19, the administration of survey questionnaires to parents' and learners' respondents was done online using google forms. With the help of the principals and teachers, the survey questionnaires were sent via messenger to each parent and pupil of Grade 5 and Grade 6. At the same time, they were ensuring research ethics such as anonymity and confidentiality. Then, after all the expected 100 parents and 100 learners' respondents submitted their answers, the researcher tallied, analyzed, and interpreted the data.

Data Analysis

The data gathered in the study was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to describe the variables in the study.

Moreover, Pearson Product Moment of Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between parenting style and support and learners' academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1: To what level the parents' and learners' respondents assess the following: Parenting Style: Authoritative and Permissive – indulgent? Support: Financial and Education?

Table 2 illustrates the descriptive statistics of parents' assessment of authoritative parenting style. It shows that the overall mean rating was 3.29 and described as Most of the Time. This means that parents' respondents' assessment of authoritative parenting style was described most of the time. It implies that parents manifested a highly authoritative parenting style in raising their children. Parents were authoritatively described with high levels of parental demand and control, likewise with high levels of warmth and communication. Authoritative parents set clear rules and expectations and have high standards yet are not over-demanding. They expect children to follow the rules and explain the reasons behind them. An authoritative parenting style is said to be the ideal parenting style, among others of its positive contributions to a child's academic performance as well as to the child's high levels of self-reliance and self-esteem, who is responsible, independent, and goal-driven individual.

According to Li (2022), authoritative parenting is described with high responsiveness and high demands. While it is very responsive to the emotional needs of its children yet has a high standard and is very consistent in enforcing boundaries of set limits. Furthermore, they listen to their children, allow reasoning with children instead of demanding them blind obedience, and use positive discipline instead of forceful punishment. Authoritative parenting earns the children's respect without demanding it.

As per indicator analysis, the indicator "I have established clear rules and restrictions for my children to follow and I explain to them the reasoning behind it in order for them to understand" obtained the highest mean rating of 3.83 and described as At All Times. It

reveals that parents established strict rules and restrictions that their children should follow. Though parents displayed controlling and demanding behavior, they were considerate and kind to their children as they explained the reasons behind established rules and restrictions so their children could understand. It implies that parents manifest high levels of demand and control, likewise with high levels of warmth and communication. At the same time, they encourage their children to give their opinion, reason and ask questions so parents can make some adjustments and exceptions to the rules and restrictions. Therefore, it can be inferred that parents treat their children with respect and consider their children's well-being.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Parents' Assessment on Authoritative Parenting Style

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	Description
	4	3	2	1		
I have established clear rules and restrictions for my children to follow and I explain to them the reasoning behind it in order for them to understand.	83	16	0	0	3.83	At all times
I encouraged my children to ask and to give their opinions if they find that family rules and restrictions were somewhat unreasonable.	38	49	11	2	3.23	Most of the times
I assigned children's tasks and gave decisions thorough reasoning and discipline.	46	43	11	0	3.35	Most of the times
I told my children my expectations from them to be aware and to find ways how to attain it.	43	39	15	3	3.22	Most of the times
I give direction and guidance in logical and open-minded ways.	51	45	4	0	3.47	Most of the times
I imposed clear standards of behavior at home for my children but I give consideration to those standards depending on the child's need.	42	49	8	1	3.32	Most of the times
I want my children to obey my directions when doing some tasks at home but I am willing to listen to their concerns and explain my directions clearly to them.	62	36	2	0	3.60	At all times
I give my children the rights to disagree with my directions with regards to their behaviors and tasks if it is necessary.	21	32	41	6	2.68	Most of the times
I admit to my children if ever I commit mistake especially hurting their feelings.	44	34	22	0	3.22	Most of the times
I consider the opinions and suggestions of my children when making family decisions.	36	30	29	5	2.97	Most of the times
	Over-all mean				3.29	Most of the times

Legend: 1.5-2.49 = Sometimes; 2.5-3.49 = Most of the time; 1.0-1.49 = Never; 3.5-4.00 = At all times

On the same thought Cherry (2017), posited that authoritative parenting is a child-centric approach. Parents hold high expectations for their children yet are backed with their support and guidance. Sometimes, this parenting style is referred to as democratic because parents also tend to be flexible with their high expectations. Parents make some adjustments depending on their child's needs as they listen to their kids and provide love and warmth responses.

Furthermore, the indicator "I give my children the rights to disagree with my directions with regards to their behaviors and tasks if it is necessary" obtained the lowest mean rating 2.68 and described as Most of the Time. It reveals that parents, most of the time, give their children the right to express their disagreement regarding directing children's behaviors and tasks if necessary. Parents give their children the opportunity to speak up and always consider their welfare. It shows that there is parent-child open communication as they discuss and exchange ideas in order to come up with a better solution. In contrast, freedom of speech is observable in their home environment yet following some strict rules and directions from their parents.

Similarly, Dewar (2017), study found authoritative parents listen to their children's concerns. They take them into account and help their children figure out what went wrong, and explain to them the consequences of good and bad behavior. Authoritative parents were not just trying to impose compliance but also encourage a child's sense of autonomy.

Table 3 illustrates the descriptive statistics of parents' assessment of permissive-indulgent parenting style. It revealed that the overall mean rating was 2.76 and described as Most of the Time. This means that parent's respondents' assessment of permissive-indulgent parenting style was described most of the time. It implies parents exercised high permissive-indulgent parenting towards their children. Parents showed low levels of demandingness but with high levels of responsiveness. Parents were friendly to their children rather than being a parent in authority, setting few rules or no limits that sometimes put the child's safety in danger. Moreover, they give their children the opportunity to enjoy their social life, allow children to make decisions without guidance from them, and permit children to do and plan activities they are interested in to achieve their realistic goals in life.

As mentioned by Moore (2017), permissive-indulgent parents have an extensive amount of parent-child communication while displaying very low levels of maturity and demand from their children. Parents tend to be more of a child's friend rather than a disciplinarian figure. Decreased maturity and independence associated with parental indulgence resulted in harm to a child's emotional development because children were not required to grow in these areas. The positive side of permissive-indulgent parents is that their children were described to have higher self-esteem, have better social skills, and experience lower levels of depression, that aids in positive social development.

As per indicator analysis, the indicator "My children are like my friend where we have a healthy open-communication" obtained the highest mean rating 3.49 and described as Most of the Time. It reveals that parents were friendly and approachable towards their children. It shows healthy and open communication inside their family because of its friendly environment. Parents displayed a high

level of responsiveness and cared for their children. In comparison, children have no difficulty in expressing their thoughts and feelings as their parents are willing to listen like a friend. It also shows that parents treat their children as equals, thus not manifesting high authority towards their children.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Parents' Assessment on Permissive-Indulgent Parenting Style

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	Description
	4	3	2	1		
I give my children the freedom of choice to obey rules and set of standards behaviors that I had imposed.	16	34	43	7	2.59	Most of the time
I allow my children to discuss their opinions and insights in the family as often as we parents do.	32	44	21	3	3.05	Most of the time
My children are like my friends where we have a healthy open- communication.	58	33	9	0	3.49	Most of the time
My children's happiness is my top priority. They can do whatever can make them happy.	46	33	17	4	3.21	Most of the time
I sometimes reminded my children about the expectations set for them and guidelines for behavior.	42	47	10	1	3.31	Most of the time
I have least expectation from my children in meeting all the expectations, I had discussed to them.	13	30	39	9	2.56	Most of the time
I am opened-minded when my children disagreed the directions or ideas, I told had them.	15	39	38	8	2.61	Most of the time
I usually agree with my children wants and suggestions when making family decisions.	10	26	53	9	2.39	Most of the time
I allow my children to decide on some matters for themselves without a lot of guidance from me.	5	24	45	26	2.08	Sometimes
I feel that my children are the one responsible to direct and to set their own behaviors as they are growing up.	10	31	35	24	2.27	Sometimes
Over-all mean					2.76	Most of the time

Legend: 1.5-2.49 = Sometimes; 2.5-3.49 = Most of the time; 1.0-1.49 = Never; 3.5-4.00 = At all times

Perry (2019) pointed out that permissive-indulgent parents were known to be warm and friendly towards their children. While their children will have a lot of fun being around them, they are granted unlimited access to have fun. Likewise, Sanvictores and Mendez (2021) stated that permissive-indulgent parents act more like friends than parents. The communication between child and parent remains open, but children were left to figure things out for themselves.

Meanwhile, the indicator “I allow my children to decide on some matters for themselves without a lot of guidance from me” obtained the lowest mean rating 2.08 and described as Sometimes. It reveals that parents sometimes allow their children to make decisions by themselves without their guidance. This is because parents consider their children to be mature individuals and in authority to decide on things that matter to them. In this sense, parents give children the freedom of choice and the opportunity to enjoy their social life and plan and do activities they are interested in in order to achieve their realistic goals in life.

According to Alexander (2017), indulgent parents allow their children to make most decisions by themselves. Parents may avoid confrontation with their kids but make a few attempts to call and direct their children's behavior. In addition, permissive-indulgent parents considered their children as equal rather than children of a parent. Whereas children do not have many responsibilities and are allowed to regulate their own behavior and decide the majority of their choices (Trautner, 2017).

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Parents' Assessment on Financial Support

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	Description
	4	3	2	1		
I make sure to financially support my children's study.	86	14	0	1	3.86	At all times
I give my children enough money for their school projects and activities.	66	24	7	3	3.53	At all times
I see to it that my children were satisfied with their daily allowance.	41	35	20	4	3.13	Most of the time
I am on time in paying my children's tuition fees obligation.	55	31	14	0	3.42	Most of the time
I give extra money for my children's personal needs.	28	30	39	3	2.83	Most of the time
I immediately give money when my children are asking for it.	5	24	53	18	2.16	Sometimes
I encourage my children to save money from daily allowance if possible.	80	15	4	1	3.75	At all times
I reminded my children not to borrow money from their classmates.	70	18	7	5	3.53	At all times
I make sure that my children can buy completely their school requirement.	75	19	5	1	3.68	At all times
I allowed my children to spend their extra allowance to their wants and needs.	22	26	41	11	2.59	Most of the time
Over-all mean					3.25	Most of the time

Legend: 1.5-2.49 = Sometimes; 2.5-3.49 = Most of the time; 1.0-1.49 = Never; 3.5-4.00 = At all times

Table 4 describes the descriptive statistics of parents' assessment on financial support. It reveals that the overall mean rating was 3.25 and described as Most of the Time. The data implies that parents have higher financial support for their children's needs most of the time. This means that parents put much consideration into supporting and financing children's needs and demand that parents may

work hard and find ways to meet it all. Parents may consider financial support for a child's education as one of their top priorities as it will affect and motivate children to strive hard at school. Nowadays, education is an investment that requires the financial stability and capacity of the parents. It might be challenging for parents, yet it is the reality.

According to Adzido et al. (2016), families having a stable financial status enhances the student's performance, such as their learning process and doing better on their academic performance. A family's socio-economic status affirms that the father's education, occupation, and income affect children's academic performance (Das & Sinha, 2017). On the other hand, parental support and involvement are pivotal to their children's school achievement and lives (Dudeja & Balda, 2019).

As per indicator analysis, the indicator "I make sure to financially support my children's study" obtained the highest mean rating 3.86 and described as At all Times. It reveals that parents at all times make sure to support their children's studies financially. It means that parents put high regard on providing for the financial needs of their schooled children. Based on the data gathered, all parents' respondents graduated from college and have a better job. Others have a business and are self-employed. In this case, parents have the capacity to sustain and finance a family's needs and may not find it too difficult to meet their needs.

Further, Movena et al. (2020) conducted a study about parental financial support and learners' motivation toward learning. It sought to investigate parents' capacity to provide financially for the student's needs in their education is referred to as parental financial support. Data revealed that learners were more motivated toward schooling when they received financial support from their parents. It shows a significant relationship between parental financial support and learners' motivation to learn at school. It means that the high level of parents' financial support affects students' motivation in learning.

Further, the indicator "I immediately give money when my children are asking for it" obtained the lowest mean rating 2.16 and described as Sometimes. It reveals that sometimes parents' respondents immediately give money to their children when asked for it. It implies that there were incidents where parents were not so responsive to children asking for money from them. Maybe, parents want to discipline and teach their children how to value and when to spend money. As young as they are, children must learn how to value money and be responsible spenders. Parents' attitudes towards money spending and saving money serve as a model to children when they grow up.

According to Morin (2021), teaching children how to earn and spend money helps them to be wise and develop self-discipline not just to prevent behavioral problems, it is also a skill that will help children when they grow up. Knowingly that children mimic their parents, and if a child observes that parents are wasting money, they are more likely they do the same as they grow up. Parents should be role models to their children.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Parents' Assessment on Education Support

Indicators	Frequency					Description	
	4	3	2	1	Mean		
I check my children's school homework regularly.	44	40	14	2	3.26	Most of the time	
I help my children in doing their homework.	19	37	40	4	2.71	Most of the time	
I evaluate and sign my child's report card progress regularly.	54	40	5	1	3.47	Most of the time	
I give commendation to my children with their good performance in academics.	57	43	0	0	3.57	At all times	
I encourage my children to join in school co-curricular activities	59	39	2	0	3.57	At all times	
I make sure that my children have time to study at home.	55	37	8	0	3.47	Most of the time	
I regularly check my children's exercise books.	32	41	24	3	3.02	Most of the time	
I motivate and encourage my children to work harder in school.	66	32	1	1	3.63	At all times	
I provide my children with learning materials and resources like exercise books, pens, pencils, and textbooks.	88	17	3	0	3.77	At all times	
I am present in parent-teacher association meetings.	39	60	1	0	3.38	Most of the time	
					Over-all mean	3.39	Most of the time

Legend: 1.5-2.49 = Sometimes; 2.5-3.49 = Most of the time; 1.0-1.49 = Never; 3.5-4.00 = At all times

Table 5 describes the descriptive statistics of parents' assessment of education support. It revealed that the overall mean rating was 3.33 and described as Most of the Time. The data implies that most of the time, parents have higher education support for their children's educational needs. It means that parents understand their responsibility towards their child's education. Their responsibility and duty are to monitor, help, guide, and commend their child's academic performance, encourage, and provide all learning materials needed at school. Parents also supported their child's co-curricular activities and attended PTA meetings at school. Parents' involvement in the educational endeavor of their children will greatly impact a child's motivational drive as it will reflect on the child's academic performance.

According to Kiral (2019), parents' most responsibilities were to provide nutrition for the whole family, ensure the children's neatness, provide clothing needs such as clothes and school uniforms, check children's homework and lessons, guiding and help their homework at home, monitoring their social activities and teaching them to acquire self-care skills. In addition, the role of parents in accordance with the school's curriculum is to support and join the extracurricular activities of the school (Cagdas et al., 2016).

As per indicator analysis, the indicator “I provide my children with learning materials and resources like exercise books, pen, pencils, and textbooks” obtained the highest mean rating 3.77 and described as At all Times. It reveals that parents at all times provide their children with all the learning materials and resources like exercise books, pens, pencils, and textbooks. This means that children have all the necessary things needed in schooling. Parents take into account to supply all tangible materials in schooling for it will supplement and support children in their learning episode as well as motivate them in their class. It is the primary duty of parents to support all the basic needs and education needs of a child.

According to Amplaya and Garcia (2019), the parent’s primary goal is to provide for their children's educational needs. Then, in return, children will strive for educational success to fulfill the filial obligation and parents’ expectations. In addition, parents who were more supportive and involved in academic activities students showed higher academic performance (Shahzad et al. (2020).

Furthermore, the indicator “I help my children do their homework” obtained the lowest mean rating of 2.71 and described as Most of the Time. It reveals that parents usually help their children do their homework. Parents set a time to help their children do homework, guide them, and monitor their child’s school work. Doing homework also serves as a venue to have academic bonding with your child where parents may notice the progress and development of learning episodes of their child. Helping children do their homework will build their confidence and assurance that they are helped and supported. They were not alone during their study as their family was the support system, and when in time of need and difficulty, their family and parents were there to help them out.

According to Kiser (2020), parents’ important responsibility to their children is helping with their homework as they can provide direct support and guidance in the learning process. Learning at home and being involved with children's academics is one of the best predictors of academic success in school. In addition, parental support for children’s homework helps them develop self-confidence and motivation in the classroom.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Learners’ Assessment on Authoritative Parenting Style

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	Description
	4	3	2	1		
My parents have established clear rules and restrictions for us to follow and explain the reasons behind it so we can understand.	58	36	5	1	3.51	At all times
My parents encouraged us to ask and to give opinions if we find that family rules an restrictions were somewhat unreasonable.	36	37	19	8	3.01	Most of the time
My parents assigned us tasks and gave decisions thorough reasoning and discipline.	53	37	9	1	3.42	Most of the time
My parents told their expectations from us so that we will be aware and find ways how to attain it.	40	42	16	2	3.20	Most of the time
My parents give us direction and guidance in logical and open- minded ways.	56	34	8	2	3.44	Most of the time
My parents imposed clear standards of behavior at home but also give their children consideration to those standards depending on our needs.	43	45	12	0	3.31	Most of the time
My parents wanted us to obey their directions when doing some tasks at home but they’re willing to listen our concerns and explain their directions clearly so we can get it.	55	34	10	1	3.43	Most of the time
My parents give us the rights to disagree with their directions with regards to our behaviors and tasks if it is necessary.	28	39	26	7	2.88	Most of the time
My parents admit their mistakes especially when they hurt our feelings.	33	27	35	7	2.86	Most of the time
My parents consider our opinions and suggestions when making family decisions.	25	38	33	4	2.84	Most of the time
	Over-all mean				3.19	Most of the time

Legend: 1.5-2.49 = Sometimes; 2.5-3.49 = Most of the time; 1.0-1.49 = Never; 3.5-4.00 = At all times

Table 6 describes the descriptive statistics of learners’ assessment of authoritative parenting style. It reveals that the overall mean rating was 3.19 and described as Most of the Time. It implies that the learner's assessment of the authoritative parenting style was described most of the time. Learners’ parents were manifesting a high authoritative in parenting. It means that learners observed and experienced the manifestation of this kind of parenting style. Their parents set clear rules, expectations and have high standards yet do not over-demanding them, and children observed that their parents explained the reasons behind their rules and restrictions, they were heard and listened to about their feelings and opinions, and also their parents admitted and acknowledged if they were wrong or committed a mistake. It shows that there is two-way communication between both parent-child.

Cited by Kulas (2017), authoritative parenting was described as firm, loving, and kind towards their children. Parents explain their set of rules and boundaries so children may understand and expect their children to follow them. Yet, neither strict nor overly indulgent, parents strike a good balance between expectations that are too high or that are too low. Moreover, they allow their children to make choices that are age-appropriate and encourage children to take on more responsibility as they grow. Thus, they are responding well to the needs of their child yet do not give in to every desire.

As per indicator analysis, the indicator “My parents have established clear rules and restrictions for us to follow and explain the reasons behind it so we can understand” obtained the highest mean rating 3.51 and described as At All Times. It implies that learners were given established clear rules and restrictions to follow but their parents explain and let them understand the reasons behind it. This

means that parents were considerate of their children as they let them understand the reasons behind established rules and restrictions that they must follow. Learners experienced high demand and control from their parents likewise with high levels of warmth and communication. Hence, they were encouraged to ask questions, to give their opinion and reason if needed to make some exceptions to the rules.

According to Kuppens and Ceulemans (2019) authoritative parents were known to have high demandingness and responsiveness. Parents express their love and acceptance toward their children, expecting children to follow given rules yet explaining the rules to help them to understand why such behaviors are unacceptable, open to hearing children's thoughts and feelings. Likewise, authoritative parents give children room to make mistakes in order to develop healthy independence as they grow older.

On the other hand, the indicator "My parents consider our opinions and suggestions when making family decisions" obtained the lowest mean rating 2.84 and described as Most of the Time. It reveals that learners' parents, most of the time, consider their opinions and suggestions when making family decisions. It also shows that parents value and respect their children's opinions. Although authoritative parents are described with high demand and control, they also possess high levels of warmth and communication. Thus, they encourage children to give their opinion and express their suggestions. As a result, parent-child communication is much more open, and all family members count and are vital during decision making.

Cited by Rego (2015), authoritative parenting may be the most appealing among parenting styles because of its well-known balance between structure and affection. Parents listen to their children while allowing children to express their feelings and opinions and encourage them to talk about options. On the other hand, authoritative parents allow their children to make their own choices that are age-appropriate, also encouraging them to take on responsibilities as they grow.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Learners' Assessment on Permissive-Indulgent Parenting Style

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	Description
	4	3	2	1		
My parents give us the freedom of choice to obey rules and set of standards behaviors they had imposed on us.	22	44	32	2	2.86	Most of the time
My parents allow us to discuss our opinions and insights in the family as often as my parents do.	23	41	33	3	2.84	Most of the time
My parents are like my friends and we have a healthy opened- communication.	53	35	11	1	3.40	Most of the time
My parents' top priority is our happiness. They want us do whatever can make us happy.	51	36	12	1	3.36	Most of the time
My parents sometimes tell us their expectations and guidelines for our behavior.	35	33	30	2	3.01	Most of the time
My parents have least expectation from us in meeting all the expectations, they had discussed on us.	15	19	53	13	2.36	Sometimes
My parents were opened-minded when their children disagreed the directions or ideas, they told on them.	20	47	30	3	2.81	Most of the time
My parents usually agree and consider on what want and suggest when making family decisions.	21	42	31	6	2.78	Most of the time
My parents allowed us to decide on some matters without a lot of guidance from them.	11	32	44	13	2.41	Sometimes
My parents feel that their children are the one responsible to direct and to set their own behaviors as they are growing up.	28	31	2	12	2.77	Most of the time
Over-all mean					2.86	Most of the time

Legend: 1.5-2.49 = Sometimes; 2.5-3.49 = Most of the time; 1.0-1.49 = Never; 3.5-4.00 = At all times

Table 7 describes the descriptive statistics of learners' assessment on permissive-indulgent parenting style. It reveals that the overall mean rating was 2.86 and described as Most of the Time. The data reveals that learners' assessment of permissive-indulgent parenting was described as most of the time or parents were high permissive-indulgent in their parenting style. Learners notice that their parents' parenting style falls to permissive-indulgent as described with low levels of demandingness but with high levels of responsiveness. Where parents set few rules or no limits, sometimes the child's safety is put in danger. But give their children the opportunity to enjoy their social life, plan and do activities they are interested in order to achieve their realistic goals in life.

Thakre (2020), added that the indulgent parenting style displays very few demands and is highly responsive to their children. They rarely discipline their children because parents have low expectations of maturity and self-control from their children. Moreover, they tend to avoid confrontation with their children; also, they allow their children to make their own decisions for themselves, while they are very responsive to their child's needs.

As per indicator analysis, the indicator "My parents are like my friends and we have a healthy open- communication" obtained the highest mean rating 3.40 and described it as Most of the Time. It reveals that children and parents are friends and have healthy open communication most of the time. This means that learners consider and see their parents as friends and can converse with each other in a healthy, open communication. Furthermore, it is very evident that parents show high levels of responsiveness towards their children. Maybe children find it comforting that they can express their thoughts and feelings without being rejected by this parent and child-friendly atmosphere.

On the other hand, permissive-indulgent parents were known to be warm and friendly towards their children. Children will have a lot of fun being around permissive-indulgent parents, for they are granted unlimited access to have fun.

Thus, permissive-indulgent parents focus more on being their child's friends than disciplinary parents. They have an extensive amount of parent-child communication yet very low levels of maturity and demands required of the child (Moore, 2017).

The indicator "My parents have least expectations from us in meeting all the expectations, they have discussed with us" obtained the lowest mean rating 2.36 and described as Sometimes. It reveals that learners' parents had the least expectations from them. It implies that learners were not obliged and demanded to meet all parents' expectations from them. Likewise, learners were not reprimanded and punished for not following or meeting parents' expectations or demands. It seems that learners can make decisions about whether they are going to meet their parents' expectations or not.

Permissive-indulgent parenting style allows their children to do just whatever they like or want. Moreover, parents have little demand from their children while mostly allowing their child to make her own decisions which creates a child who lacks self-control (Ireland, 2018). As a result, children of permissive parents tend to grow up without a strong sense of self-discipline and be more unruly in school due to the lack of boundaries from home and likely less academically motivated than many of their peers (Cherry, 2021).

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Learners' Assessment on Financial Support

Indicators	Frequency					Description	
	4	3	2	1	Mean		
My parents make sure to financially support our study.	73	16	11	0	3.62	At all times	
My parents give us enough money for our school projects and activities.	56	33	7	4	3.41	Most of the time	
My parents see to it that we're satisfied with our daily allowance	44	39	13	4	3.23	Most of the time	
My parents are on time in paying our tuition fees obligation.	56	35	9	0	3.47	Most of the time	
My parents give use extra money for our personal needs.	28	23	42	7	2.72	Most of the time	
My parents immediately give us money when we ask for it.	10	19	53	18	2.21	Sometimes	
My parents encourage us to save money from our daily allowance if possible.	64	25	7	4	3.49	Most of the time	
My parents remind us not to borrow money from our classmates.	51	20	16	13	3.09	Most of the time	
My parents make sure that we can buy completely our school requirement.	70	21	7	2	3.59	At all times	
My parents allowed us to spend our extra allowance to our wants and needs.	29	18	45	8	2.68	Most of the time	
	Over-all mean					3.15	Most of the time

Legend: 1.5-2.49 = Sometimes; 2.5-3.49 = Most of the time; 1.0-1.49 = Never; 3.5-4.00 = At all times

Table 8 describes the descriptive statistics of learners' assessment on financial support. It reveals that the overall mean rating was 3.15 and described as Most of the Time. It reveals that learners' assessment of financial support was described most of the time. It means that learners' parents have higher financial support for them. It shows that learners observed that their parents supported them financially, such as paying their tuition fees and giving money if they asked for personal, school projects, and other school needs. At the same time, learners appreciate their parents for working hard to finance their basic needs and school needs. When students receive adequate finances, their academic performance may enhance compared to those students that received inadequate financial support their academic performance was affected. On the other hand, when the family's financial status is stable, children's school performance becomes better and enhances their learning process (Adzido, 2016).

As per indicator analysis, the indicator "My parents make sure to financially support our study" obtained the highest mean rating 3.62 and described as At all Times. It reveals that learners at all times were supported financially by their parents. Where learners received sufficient financial support for their education needs as their parents put regard on their education. More so, parents work hard in order to support and finance their children, for it is their desire to give what's best for their children.

According to Movena et al. (2020), parents' capacity to provide financially for the student's needs in their education is referred to as parental financial support. Data revealed that learners were more motivated toward schooling when they received financial support from their parents. It shows a significant relationship between parental financial support and learners' motivation to learn at school. It means that the high level of parents' financial support affects students' motivation in learning.

Further, the indicator "My parents immediately give us money when we ask for it" obtained the lowest mean rating of 2.21 and described as Sometimes. It reveals that learners' parents sometimes immediately give money to them when asked for it. It implies that parents are not so responsive to their children if they ask for money from them. Perhaps, parents teach their children to spend on essential things only or discipline and teach them to value.

Table 9 describes the descriptive statistics of learners' assessment on education support. It revealed that the overall mean rating was 3.29 and described as Most of the Time. The data implies that learners most of the time received higher education support from parents. It means that learners' parents were active and involved in their children's educational journey. Parents exert support on children's education in terms of monitoring, helping, guiding, encouraging, and providing school needs materials, while parents participate in school meetings such as PTA meetings. In addition, children were commended for good academic performance by their parents,

wherein they are morally motivated as well.

Table 9. Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Learners' Assessment on Parents' Education Support

Indicators	Frequency					Description	
	4	3	2	1	Mean		
My parents check our school homework regularly.	42	36	18	4	3.16	Most of the time	
My parents help us in doing our homework.	29	29	36	6	2.79	Most of the time	
My parents evaluate and sign our report card progress regularly	41	34	24	1	3.15	Most of the time	
My parents give their children a commendation of having a good performance in academics.	51	48	1	0	3.50	At all times	
My parents encourage us to join in school co-curricular activities.	36	64	1	0	3.35	Most of the time	
My parents make sure that we have time to study at home.	56	29	12	3	3.38	Most of the time	
My parents regularly check our exercise books.	29	33	30	8	2.83	Most of the time	
My parents motivate and encourage us to work harder in school.	66	28	5	1	3.59	At all times	
My parents provide us with learning materials and resources like exercise books, pen, pencils, and text books.	81	16	3	0	3.78	At all times	
My parent/s are present in PTA meetings.	48	42	10	0	3.38	Most of the time	
	Over-all mean					3.29	Most of the time

Legend: 1.5-2.49 = Sometimes; 2.5-3.49 = Most of the time; 1.0-1.49 = Never; 3.5-4.00 = At all times

When parents were highly involved with their children's schooling, such as asking the child about what happened in school, checking if they have homework, as well as checking up on the child's activities, and providing structure at home that helps their children to perform well at school. In addition, parents' motivation also has a great impact on student's educational success (Ozen, 2017), and parents' moral support for children will encourage and motivate them to perform well at school (Shahzad et al., 2020).

As per indicator analysis, the indicator "My parents provide us with learning materials and resources like exercise books, pen, pencils, and textbooks" obtained the highest mean rating 3.78 and described as At all Times. It reveals that learners at all times were provided with learning materials and resources like exercise books, pens, pencils, and textbooks by their parents. It means that all learners' educational materials and resources needed were all available. Children have nothing to worry about when it comes to their school materials and resources as they are well-provided. Parents understand that their primary role in children's education is to provide educational support as to their basic needs.

Thus, the parent's primary goal is to provide for the educational needs of their children. Then, in return, children will strive for educational success to fulfill filial obligations and parent's expectations. The family's strong engagement in early childhood education, systems, and programs is suggested as central, not supplemental, in promoting children's healthy intellectual, solid and healthy physical, as well as social-emotional development; also preparing children for school, and supporting and guiding in their academic achievement in elementary school and beyond (Kelly, 2020).

Furthermore, the indicator "My parents help us in doing our homework" obtained the lowest mean rating 2.79 and described as Most of the time. It reveals that learners were encouraged by parents to often share about their teachers most of the time. It means their parents were interested to know about their teachers and wanted to be updated about school matters. Perhaps, parents just want to have a parent-child conversation bonding to know their perceptions and attitudes towards their teacher and their school experiences.

Cited by Kiser (2020), helping children's homework is a parent's important responsibility as they can provide direct support and guidance in the learning process. Pointed out that learning at home and being involved with children's academics is one of the best predictors of academic success in school. Parental support on children's homework will help them to develop self-confidence and motivation in their class. Furthermore, helping students with homework has many benefits such as spending quality and individual time with children, defining strengths and weaknesses, learning becoming more meaningful, and setting higher aspirations.

Table 10 shows the summary of parents' and learners' assessment of parenting styles and support, which is discussed in different domains, and overall, the parents' assessment of parenting styles as indicated by the overall mean rating of 3.025 (SD = 0.75) and described as "Most of the time." While learner's assessment of parenting styles is indicated by the overall mean rating of 3.025 (SD = 0.81) and described as "Most of the time."

On the other hand, parents' assessment of support was indicated by the overall mean rating of 3.32 (SD = 0.68) and described as "Most of the time," while learners' assessment of support was indicated by the overall mean rating of 3.22 (SD = 0.82) and described as "Most of the time."

The findings show that parents most of the time manifested a high level of authoritative parenting style and the same with permissive-indulgent parenting style. At the same time, the learners confirmed on their assessment that they experienced the same level of parenting styles from their parents based on their assessment. On the other hand, in terms of the parents' support, it reveals that parents have a high level of support towards their children most of the time. The learners' assessment of the support also suggested that they received a high level of support from their respective parents.

Table 10. Summary of the Level of Parents' and Learners' Assessment of Parenting Styles and Support

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Parents' assessment on Parenting Styles:			
Authoritative	3.29	0.69	Most of the time
Permissive-Indulgent	2.76	0.81	Most of the time
Overall Mean	3.025	0.75	Most of the time
Learner' assessment on Parenting Styles:			
Authoritative	3.19	0.79	Most of the time
Permissive-Indulgent	2.86	0.83	Most of the time
Overall Mean	3.025	0.81	Most of the time
Parents' assessment on Support:			
Financial	3.25	0.73	Most of the time
Education	3.39	0.63	Most of the time
Overall Mean	3.32	0.68	Most of the time
Learner' assessment on Support:			
Financial	3.15	0.84	Most of the time
Education	3.29	0.79	Most of the time
Overall Mean	3.22	0.82	Most of the time

Legend: 1.5-2.49 = Sometimes; 2.5-3.49 = Most of the time; 1.0-1.49 = Never; 3.5-4.00 = At all times

The indicator "authoritative parenting style" on parents' assessment obtained the highest overall mean rating of 3.29 (SD = 0.69) and described as Most of the time. The learners' assessment also obtained the highest overall mean rating 3.19 (SD = 0.79) and described as Most of the time as well. It reveals that parents' respondents most of the time were highly authoritative on their parenting, maybe of the reasons that parents were aware of its positive effect on their children. Meanwhile, learners' respondents reveal that they experienced and received most of the time authoritative parenting based on their assessment. The authoritative parenting style, is described with high levels of parental demand and control, likewise with high levels of warmth and communication. Parents set clear rules and expectations, have high standards yet are not over-demanding; expect their children to follow the rules and explain the reasons behind them; encourage their children to ask questions to give opinions and reasons if needed. Children of authoritative parents are described with high levels of self-reliance and self-esteem and are responsible, independent, and goal-driven individuals.

Moreover, to Kuppens and Ceulemans (2019); (Checa and Gutierrez, 2018) parenting styles, authoritative parenting claimed popularity as the most effective style to rear a child, as concluded by some studies. It has been proven of its association with positive outcomes for children. Tanvir et al.'s (2016) findings revealed that the authoritative parenting style has more effect on learners' academic performance as compared to authoritarian and permissive parenting styles. Additionally, Alnafea and Curtis (2017) revealed that the authoritative parenting style was linked to enhanced cognitive and metacognitive strategy, time and study management, and self-efficacy.

Furthermore, the indicator "permissive-indulgent parenting style" on parents' assessment obtained the lowest overall mean rating of 2.76 (SD = 0.81) and described as most of the time. The learners' assessment also obtained the lowest overall mean rating 2.86 (SD = 0.83), and described as most of the time. It reveals that both parents and learners have the same level of assessment of permissive-indulgent parenting style as described most of the time. A permissive-indulgent parenting style is described with low levels of demandingness but with high levels of responsiveness towards their children. While parents set few rules or no limits, sometimes the child's safety is put in danger; they give their children the opportunity to enjoy and plan activities for their social; low expectations on the child's academic performance; often, no reprimand or consequence when misbehaving for not following rules; parents were friendly to their children more than being a parent in authority. As a result, their children display immaturity, demanding, and undisciplined behavior.

As a matter of fact, to Perry (2019), permissive-indulgent parents are known to be warm and friendly, and their children have a lot of fun being around them, for they are granted unlimited access to have fun. At the same time, parents act more like friends than parents. The communication between child and parent remains open, but children are left to figure things out for themselves. In addition, permissive-indulgent parents have an extensive amount of parent-child communication while displaying very low levels of maturity and demand from their children. Parents tend to be more of a child's friend rather than a disciplinarian figure. Decreased maturity and independence associated with parental indulgence resulted in harm to a child's emotional development because children were not required to grow in these areas. Still, there is a positive side to permissive-indulgent parents said that their children were described to have higher self-esteem, having better social skills, and experience lower levels of depression, which aids in positive social development (Moore, 2017).

Meanwhile, the indicator "education support" on parents' assessment obtained the highest overall mean rating of 3.39 (SD = 0.63) and described as Most of the time. The learners' assessment also obtained the highest overall mean rating 3.29 (SD = 0.79) and described as Most of the time. It reveals that parents have high support in terms of education. While learners agreed on their assessment that their

parents gave them high support with regards to their educational needs. This implies that parents consider their child’s education as one of their top priorities and that they understand when children are given adequate support and guidance, they are motivated to do well in school and strive for academic success. On the other hand, children were striving hard in order to fulfill their school obligations and having a good performance report to their parents as their way of giving back all the favor, love, support, and guidance that they have received from their parents.

Pointed out by Kiral (2019) that parents' most responsibilities to their family are to provide nutrition for the whole family, ensure the children’s neatness, provide clothing needs such as clothes and school uniforms, check children’s homework and lessons, guide and help their homework at home, monitoring their social activities and teaching them to acquire self-care skills. Parents were highly involved with their children's schooling, such as asking the child about what happened in school, checking if they have homework, as well as checking up on the child’s activities, and providing structure at home it helps their children to perform well at school (Garcia & de Guzman, 2020).

Furthermore, the indicator “financial” on parents’ assessment obtained the lowest overall mean rating of 3.25 (SD = 0.73) and described as Most of the times. The learners’ assessment also obtained the lowest overall mean rating 3.15 (SD = 0.84) and described as Most of the times. It reveals that parents most of the time have a high support for the financial needs of their children. The data revealed that even it obtained the lowest mean rating, yet not too low in respect of its mean to the education support having the highest mean. It implies that parents’ findings ways and doing their best to support their children financially. It can be drawn that financial support is crucial and essential to education support. Children that were well provided in terms of their financial needs were likely to perform well at school compared to those who were not.

Contested by Rogone (2018), children that belong to low socioeconomic households or with families that were not financially stable were not experiencing the same education compared to those children whose parents have stable finances. Due to parents who cannot afford to support them financially, many children are struggling from the lack of resources, parents’ guidance, and the support they need in order to become just as successful as the students. On the other hand, Adzido et al. (2016) stated that families having a stable financial status enhanced the student’s performance, such as their learning process and doing better on their academic performance. A family’s socio-economic status affirms that the father’s education, occupation, and income affect children’s academic performance. On the other hand, parental support and involvement are pivotal to their children's school achievement and lives (Dudeja & Balda, 2019).

Problem 2. What is the level of learner’s academic performance in the following areas: Mathematics, Science; and English?

Table 11. *Descriptive Statistics on Learners' Academic Performance In Mathematics, Science, and English in the First and Second Quarter*

Grade Range	First Grading			Second Grading			f	%	Description	
	Math	Sci	Eng	Math	Sci	Eng				
90-100	71	84	85	81	87	90	498	0.83	Outstanding	
85-89	27	14	13	17	11	8	90	0.15	Very Satisfactory	
80-84	2	2	2	2	2	2	12	0.02	Satisfactory	
75-79	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Fairly Satisfactory	
74 and below	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Did Not Meet Expectations	
Mean	90.68	91.57	91.74	91.33	92.29	92.69	Over-all Mean		Outstanding	
								91.72		

Legend: 90 – 100%, Outstanding; 85 – 89%, Very Satisfactory; 80 – 84%, Satisfactory; 75 – 79%, Fairly Satisfactory; 74% and below, Did not meet Expectation

Table 11 describes the descriptive statistics on learners’ academic performance In Mathematics, Science, and English in the First and Second Quarter. It reveals that the overall mean rating was 91.72 and described as Outstanding. The data reveals that learners’ academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English in the First and Second Quarter, eighty-three percent (.83%) of the learners’ respondents had an Outstanding grade performance, fifteen (.15%) had a very satisfactory grade performance, while only two percent (.02%) had a satisfactory grade performance. It means that most of the learners’ respondents had acquired and developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks. While only a few learners have developed the essential knowledge and skills and core understandings while needing a little guidance from the teacher and/or with some help from peers, while being able to transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks (K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum. DepEd Order No.73, s. 2012 Guidelines on the Assessment and Rating of the Learning Outcomes and DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015, implemented the new grading system for learner’s report cards with descriptor and grading scale).

The findings revealed that most of the learners respondents achieved outstanding academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English. It shows that parents were highly involved with their children's academics as they had provided them adequate support in terms of finances and education, together with appropriate manifestation of parenting style. On the other hand, learners were mostly academically inclined as they could obtain outstanding grades in the three subjects. Learners’ may have found Mathematics enjoyable and not too difficult as well as English and Science may be because they had already acquired the advanced basic knowledge or

learnings during their early years; while there is a strong support system provided by the parents or family. Likewise, learners may develop good study habits and have a positive attitude towards those particular subjects so they can excel academically. Perhaps, learners may like those subjects and exert more effort to achieve good grades. Moreover, their parents may be consistent with their efforts in supporting and helping their children's academic performance, which positively influences children's academic achievements.

According to Narad and Abdullah (2016) stated that academic performance was the learner's gained knowledge which is assessed by marks by a teacher, or it is educational goals set by learners and teachers needed to be achieved over a particular period. Moreover, these goals were measured using continuous assessment and/or examination results. Furthermore, Dudeja and Balda (2019) expressed that learners' study habits are associated with parental involvement. Their findings showed that higher parental involvement in their children developed better study habits and attitudes. It was revealed that there was a significant association between parental involvement and the overall study habits of children. At the same time, it suggested that parental support and involvement are pivotal to their children's achievement in school and their lives.

As per subject analysis, learners' academic performance in the First and Second Quarters in Mathematics, Science, and English. It revealed that in the First Quarter, English obtained the highest mean rating, 91.74. While in the Second Quarter, English still obtained the highest mean rating 92.69, both in the First and Second Quarters were described as "Outstanding." It implies learners' academic performance or grades in English is outstanding. This means learners are doing well in English subjects and have developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks. In addition, when learners receive support from their parents or parents are involved in their child's education, children do well in school as it will reflect on her or their academic achievement.

Furthermore, Hassan and Mohammed (2016) findings on the relationship between parenting practices and primary pupils' academic achievement. Learners' academic achievement in eight subjects such as English, Mathematics, Primary Science, Social Studies, Writing, Hausa (a local language), Physical Education, as well as Art and Craft. Findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between parenting practices and primary school pupils' academic achievement. It was concluded that the academic performance of the learners is said to be dependent on many factors, whereas parenting practices are among those factors. With correct parenting style approach and application, it will yield a higher possibility of the learners getting good results and vice-versa

Furthermore, learners' academic performance in the First and Second Quarter in Mathematics, Science, and English. It reveals that in the First Quarter, Mathematics obtained the lowest mean rating, 90.68. While in the Second Quarter, still Mathematics obtained the lowest mean rating 91.33 in the second quarter, whereas both the First and Second Quarter was described as "Outstanding." Even if it obtained the lowest mean rating and standard deviation, data implies learners' academic performance or grades in Mathematics are still outstanding. This means learners are doing well in Mathematics subjects and have developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks. When learners receive support from their parents or parents are involved in their child's education, children do well in school as it will reflect on her or his academic achievement.

So, parents' involvement in their children's education is great because it enhances academic performance. Children tend to be more concentrated on school tasks. When parents are highly involved and supportive in their child's education, the child will react positively. Thus, it will reflect on her or his academic achievement. Schooled children must need to possess good study habits in order to excel in life because it is the study habits of the learners that aid in obtaining relevant and applicable knowledge. They are noted that the absence of these skills would lead to the poor academic performance of the child in school (Kaur & Pathania, 2015).

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the parenting style and support on learners' academic performance in Mathematics, Science and English?

Table 12. *Inferential Statistics on Significant Relationship Between the Parenting Styles on Learners' Academic Performance*

<i>Learners' Academic Performance in</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>Sig(P-values)</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Mathematics	-0.006	.952	Not Significant
Science	-0.022	.828	Not Significant
English	0.019	.851	Not Significant

Legend: r=result of the Pearson product-moment of correction P= probability value

Table 12 displays inferential statistics on the relationship between parenting style and parents' profiles. Pearson product-moment of correction was conducted to determine the relationship between the two variables.

The result of the analysis shows that learners' academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English was not statistically significant in relation to parenting styles since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Generally, based on the overall results, it disclosed that learners' academic performance has no significant association and influential effect on the parenting styles manifested or used by parents in raising and nurturing their children. Although parents were high on authoritative parenting was found not statistically significant to academic performance. Authoritative parenting was the most

ideal and confirmed by many researchers that it has a significant effect on academic performance. Compared to permissive-indulgent, many studies revealed that it has a negative effect on academic performance.

A contrary finding of Hassan and Mohammed (2016) disclosed a significant relationship between parenting practices and elementary pupils' academic achievement. Learners' academic achievement in eight subjects such as English, Mathematics, Primary Science, Social Studies, Writing, Hausa (a local language), Physical Education, and Art and Craft revealed a significant relationship between parenting practices and primary school pupils' academic achievement. It was concluded that the learners' academic performance depends on many factors, whereas parenting practices are among those factors. The correct parenting style approach and application will yield a higher possibility of the learners getting good results and vice-versa.

Table 13. *Inferential Statistics on Significant Relationship Between the Parental Support on Learners' Academic Performance*

<i>Learners' Academic Performance in</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>Sig(P-values)</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Mathematics	0.231 (*)	.020	Significant
Science	0.155	.123	Not Significant
English	0.210 (*)	.036	Significant

Legend: r=result of the Pearson product-moment of correlation P= probability value

Table 13 displays inferential statistics on the relationship between parental support and learners' academic performance. Pearson product-moment of correlation was conducted to determine the relationship between the two variables. The result of the analysis shows that learners' academic performance in Science has no statistically significant relationship to parental support since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Meanwhile, learners' academic performance in Mathematics and English has a significant relationship to parental support. In Mathematics it has the computed $r = 0.231 (*)$ ($p = .020$) and in English has the computed $r = 0.210(*)$ ($p = 0.36$). These two variables have a P-value lower than the alpha of 0.05, which implies that this variable has a statistically significant relationship to parental support. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Mathematics and English are found to have a significant relationship to parental support. Parental support plays an important factor in the academic performance of their children in particular subjects. Mathematics subject is a challenging subject for young learners because it involves mathematical operations and fundamental skills in order for learners can perform and do mathematical computations and solve problems. At the same time, English subject also a challenging subject, especially if this is not the first language. Furthermore, this subject has a lot of rules to remember and follow that learners should know. With these, parents' support is very significant to learners in order to excel and perform well. Thus, parents need to exert more effort in helping and guiding them to understand and acquire more skills and knowledge. Parents must not just rely on teachers but rather act as partner teachers for the children. Parental involvement and support have a crucial role in the child's schooling, for it will serve as a motivational drive for the child to strive hard, perform well at school, and aim for academic success.

According to Pianta, Downer, and Hamre (2016), Mathematics is one of the needed skills that everyone should acquire in order to become functional literate individuals. Aside from literacy (reading and writing), numeracy is a basic skill that everyone has to master as a tool for survival in day-to-day living and interacting with the community. In early education, researchers have long raised concerns about learning opportunities young children have – how often educators engage children to support their learning and growth, and with quality.

The findings of this study are in agreement with the previous studies in finding that cognitive involvement and behavioral involvement were proved to have a significant and direct impact on Mathematics achievement (Kung & Lee, 2016). It means that when parents were more involved in their children's academic performance and also place greater importance on their children's school progress. It does contribute to improving their child's Mathematics performance. On the other hand, a study revealed its findings that different dimensions of parental involvement had different effects on Mathematics achievement, while results indicated that parental involvement influences on Mathematics achievement were either partially or completely mediated by learners' mental health and Mathematics self-efficacy (Huang et al., 2021)

According to Dawn (2015), parents' aspiration is essential to support children's education while the parents act as the lead agent in their children's academic endeavors. Parents' aspirations and expectations of parents on children play an important role for it will encourage and motivate their children to strive for high academic achievement. Likewise, parents' high aspirations toward English education will surely promote children's interest to learn and master the language. Moreover, according to Amplaya and Garcia (2019), parents' primary goal is to provide for their children's educational needs. Then, in return, children will strive for educational success to fulfill the filial obligation and parent's expectations. In addition, parents who were more supportive and involved in academic activities students showed higher academic performance (Shahzad et al. (2020).

Conclusions

In the light of the above-cited findings, conclusions were drawn:

The data revealed that parents' respondents were high authoritative in their parenting style.

In view of the level of learners' academic performance in Mathematics, Science, and English in the First and Second Quarters, the English subject obtained the highest mean and described as outstanding.

The data showed that there was no significant relationship between parenting styles and the level of learners' academic performance. On the other hand, parental support and the level of learners' academic performance in Science there was no significant relationship. Meanwhile, in Mathematics and English, it was found to have a significant relationship to parental support.

On the basis of the findings and conclusions, the following are recommendations were made:

School principals must encourage parents to adopt and practice an authoritative parenting style for it has a good impact on children's academic performance. In addition, they must organize a parenting seminar to give more information and knowledge on what are the best practices of parenting and support of parents to their children.

Teachers must motivate parents to be more involved in their children's academics. Then, teacher-parent communication must be strengthened for it is beneficial for both and especially to learners.

Parents must understand that parenting and support are very important factors in a child's life while preparing them for their future. Hence, parental support must be maintained and strengthened for its great impact on their children's academic performance at school. Moreover, parents should practice and adopt authoritative parenting for its positive approaches that will influence their child's well-being.

Future research on parenting styles and support among learners should be conducted in a wider range of other schools, both private and public, of the division of Cagayan de Oro City.

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